

String search for each database

ACM	((KAOS OR "Knowledge Acquisition in Automated Specification") AND Requirements AND (goal modeling OR goal modelling OR goal-oriented OR Goal model) AND ((extension OR extend OR extended OR extensibility) OR (pattern OR profile OR approach OR process OR method)))
El Compedex	(KAOS OR "Knowledge Acquisition in Automated Specification") AND Requirements AND (goal modeling OR goal modelling OR goal-oriented OR goal model) AND ((extension OR extend OR extended OR extensibility) OR (pattern OR profile OR approach OR process OR method))
IEEE Xplore	(KAOS OR "Knowledge Acquisition in Automated Specification") AND Requirements AND (goal modeling OR goal modelling OR goal-oriented OR goal model) AND ((extension OR extend OR extended OR extensibility) OR (pattern OR profile OR approach OR process OR method))
Science Direct	((KAOS OR {Knowledge Acquisition in Automated Specification}) AND (extension OR extend OR extended OR extensibility OR approach OR method))
SCOPUS	TITLE-ABS-KEY ((KAOS OR "Knowledge Acquisition in Automated Specification") AND Requirements AND ("goal modeling" OR "goal modelling" OR goal-oriented OR goal model) AND ((extension OR extend OR extended OR extensibility) OR (pattern OR profile OR approach OR process OR method)))
Springer	(KAOS OR "Knowledge Acquisition in Automated Specification") AND Requirements AND ("goal modeling" OR "goal modelling" OR "goal-oriented" OR "goal model") AND ((extension OR extends OR extended OR extensibility) OR (pattern OR profile OR approach OR process OR method))

Steps to search for each database

ACM	<p>https://dl.acm.org/</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Access advanced search in the home page; 2. In the Search within field, select Title and paste the search string (part of the title) into the associated text field; 3. Select the option + close to search with field; 4. In the new Search within field, select Abstract and paste the search string (part of the abstract) into the associated text field; 5. Select + right after the second search with text field; 6. In the new Search within field, select Author Keyword and paste the search string (part of Keyword) into the associated text field; 7. Select the search button. 8. Select Edit Search on the results screen; 9. Select view query syntax; 10. Replace AND with OR between the Title, abstract and Keyword tags; 11. Click on the Search button
EI Compedex	<p>https://www.engineeringvillage.com/</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. On the home page, select search (in the menu) and then expert; 2. Paste the string into the search field, then click on date and refine the search by year of publication by changing the field, defining the search for articles from 1990-2021; 3. Click on the search button; 4. On the results page, refine the search by language (selecting English) and by document type (selecting Conference article and journal article).
IEEE Xplore	<p>https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. On the home page, click on advanced search; 2. Click on command search; 3. Paste the search string into the search field and click search. 4. change end year to 2021 and select conference and journal.
Science Direct	<p>https://www.sciencedirect.com/</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. On the home page, click on advanced search; 2. Click show all fields; 3. Paste the string into the search field for Title, abstract or author-specified keywords; 4. Enter 1990-2021 in the Year field 5. click on the Search button. 6. In Subject areas, select computer Science, Engineering and Mathematics. 7. In Article Type select Research articles
SCOPUS	<p>https://www.scopus.com/</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. On the home page, select advanced document search; 2. Paste the search string into the query string; 3. On the results page, refine the search by language (selecting English)

Springer	<p>http://link.springer.com/</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none">1. On the home page, paste the search string into the search field and click the search button;2. Click on published date and add 1990-2021 in the field to refine the search3. Refine the search by language (selecting English).4. Then combine the discipline fields for the computer Science and engineering values and content type for the conference paper and article values:<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Computer science & Conference Paper- Computer science & Article- Engineering & Conference Paper- Engineering & Article
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